

Comparative Study Of Labour Utilization Pattern In Cooperative And Non-Cooperative Sectors Regarding Dairying Activities And Their Association With Productivity And Employment Opportunities

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Abstract

As the title suggest an intensive time and motion study In respect of all the activities essential for operating any dairy enterprise was conducted to investigate whether one should opt for PCDF sector (Cooperative) or Non PCDF sector (Non Cooperative) for the same and the results were that labourer input a required in PCDF sector was recorded about 20% higher than non-PCDF sector yet when it was associated with the yield it was revealed that better care and management as well as availing Cooperative community facilities, the same set of livestock can give better yield and side by side can generate most employment opportunities in the shape of more time investment per milch animal per day and thus it came out as economically more viable comparative yield** in both the sectors in case of buffaloes, was 5.82 litre/4.97litre, for local Cow 3.36 litre/3.51 litre for crossbred Cows 9.23 litr/7.54 litre respectively for PCDF and Non PCDF sectors. No doubt the absolute M.M invested were recorded 98.45 MM in PCDF sector and 78.35MM in Non PCDF sectors per milch animal per day. but the figures of resultant productivity or claim that PCDF sector is recommended for the species of buffalo's and crossbred Cow's without any further micro detailing.

Keywords Co-operative, Milch Yield, Chaffing, Grazing, Feeding, Hired, Draught, Young stock, Crossbred Cow's.

Introduction After two decade of independence even our country was behind in respect of milk production and per capita milk availability as well to cope with the situation. Operation Flood was started in 1970 and since then our production has been scaling new heights on an on with the results that as per data for the year 2021-22 India has become the largest producer of milk globally with a share of 24% of total world milk production. Per capita milk availability in our country was computed as 444 gms per day while global average was only 322gms per day as per data compiled for 2121-22. These remarkable changes or reversal of situation was possible only due to the development of cooperative dairying after inception of operation flood. The role of cooperative society formed for this purpose was to provide latest know how regarding etc. and to develop marketing net work also just to optimized the labour input and returned as well for the producers of milk at large. Keeping in view the above fact this study was conducted to assured to comparative labour utilization pattern in cooperative and non-cooperative sectors and its association with productivity generation of employment opportunities. Activity-wise time study was conducted just to calculate total time or man minute required to accomplish all the activity for both the sectors separately, so that man power requirements be computed for any units and trends according to the size of the holding were also analysed for the selection of optimum herd size. Seasonal variation were also analysed so that labour requirements in respect of different seasons may be projected and arranged for accordingly. Inferences drawn after the study on the above lines are being given here under. The main inference after the study came out was that for dairying activities cooperative sector is better as compared to non-cooperative sector in the shape of better yield, returned and generation of employment opportunity as well for family labour including women primarily and available hired labour simultaneously.

**See Appendix

Aim of study

The objective of this paper is to study Comparative Study of Labour Utilization Pattern in Cooperative and Non-Cooperative Sectors Regarding Dairying Activities and Their Association with Productivity and Employment Opportunities.

Review of Literature

Kumari Binita & Malhotra Ravindra (2016)- The study revealed that 84.58 Man-minute was spent under cooperative members while 82.78 Man-minute was spent in Non-member Co-operative per milch animal per day. Coefficient for conversion of total time spent into human hours is $4.61/5.85=0.788$ in case of member and it is $4.13/5.31=0.777$. Man-minutes calculation as operation wise as under. Overall average animal size per household is 3.24 under member group and 2.97 in Non-member group.
MM/day/animal = Operation wise total human hours x coefficient x 60/Overall animal size per household. Thus the activity wise figures as computed in MM equivalent are as under.

Operations	Members co-operative					Non-members (Non-cooperative)				
	Man	Women	Child	Total Hours/day	Total MM/day/ animal	Man	Women	Child	Total Hours/day	Total MM/day/ animal
Bringing fodder	0.48	0.32	0.06	0.87	12.69	0.39	0.29	0.07	0.76	12.02
Chaffing cutting	0.29	0.35	0.06	0.71	10.36	0.27	0.32	0.06	0.66	10.36
Feeding	0.27	0.33	0.06	0.67	9.77	0.21	0.25	0.07	0.54	8.47
Grazing	0.31	0.26	0.05	0.62	9.04	0.26	0.26	0.06	0.59	9.26
Giving water	0.14	0.19	0.06	0.40	5.83	0.09	0.17	0.05	0.31	4.86
Cleaning shed & animal	0.11	0.33	0.03	0.48	7.00	0.07	0.34	0.04	0.46	7.22
Health care	0.15	0.12	0.04	0.31	4.52	0.13	0.11	0.06	0.31	4.86
Milking	0.21	0.18	-	0.39	5.69	0.15	0.22	-	0.38	5.96
Making milk products	0.05	0.37	0.02	0.45	6.56	0.06	0.38	0.03	0.48	7.53
Selling milk	0.13	0.30	0.03	0.45	6.56	0.27	0.12	0.04	0.43	6.75
Misc. work	0.18	0.21	0.07	0.45	6.56	0.11	0.15	0.09	0.35	5.49
Total time spent	2.34	3.00	0.51	5.85	84.58	2.05	2.65	0.60	5.31	82.78
Human hours	2.34	2.01	0.25	4.61		2.05	1.77	0.30	4.31	

Kashish et.al (2017) - The findings of the research study revealed that the total labour used was calculate on overall basis was 5.68 hours/day person for performing all the operation for the dairy animals. The operations-wise figures are as under.

Sr.No.	Particulars	Landless	Marginal	Small	Others	Overall
1	Cutting/bringing fodder from market/field	1.93	2.49	2.01	2.61	2.17
2	Chaff cutting of fodder	0.55	0.68	0.86	0.91	0.54
3	Grazing	0.50*	0.15*	-	-	0.14
4	Feeding & giving water	0.52	0.60	0.80	0.61	0.58
5	Cleaning cattle shed	0.65	0.67	0.95	0.86	0.77
6	Milking animal	0.76	0.83	1.06	1.02	0.92
7	Handling milk	0.33	0.33	0.39	0.34	0.32
8	Marketing of milk and milk product	0.39	0.23	0.25	0.25	0.24
9	Total labour used	5.63	5.98	6.32	6.60	5.68

Operation-wise the labour employed ranged between 5.63 hours to 6.60 hours per day and varied directly to holding size of the farmers. Grazing practice is carried out by few landless and marginal farmers. Fodder cutting and bringing fodder activity spent maximum time i.e, 2.17 hours/day among all the operation in dairy farming.

*Only four and one respondents took their animal for a grazing among landless (LL) and Marginal (M.F.) dairy farmers. respectively.

Source, Kashish et.al, 2016.

*M.M equivalent on the basis of above table for all categories combined is computer as $5.68 \times 60 = 340.80$ M.M.

Singh Rishikanta KH and Chauhan A.K (2014)- The study was concluded that on an average member cooperative consumed 4.03 hours/day for dairy activities which is equivalent to 3.75 person hour. On the other hand, the non member group utilized on an average 3.38 hours/day on dairying which is equivalent to 3.13 person hours operation wise time consumed in various dairy operation were calculated and is presented here under (hours/day)

Category	Different Activities								In person (hr.)
	Feeding animal	Cooking dana	Cleaning shed	Milking animal	Selling milk	Health care	Misc. work	Total time (hrs)	
Members	1.30	0.73	0.81	0.40	0.34	0.16	0.29	4.03	3.75
Non-members	1.05	0.52	0.67	0.36	0.35	0.13	0.29	3.38	3.13

Man-minute equivalent on the basis of above table is computed as 225 per cooperative sector and 188 for Non-cooperative sectors respectively the findings are this matching with our study.

Agrawal and Sharma (1983) Conducted a study on labour utilization pattern for dairying among season in village around Karnal. The analysis of study indicated that dairy family

labour and paid labour was utilized the time averaged 156 man-minute and 17 minute for the activity of milking. It was inferred through the study that female section of the society were up keep the higher labour input of their animals.

Singh (1986) The result showed that time was spent on different dairy activities on crossbred cattle i.e, 134.91Man-minutes followed by buffaloes (127.38 man-minutes) and local cattle (101.11 Man-minutes) Further the labour utilization pattern comprised of time spent in milking all feeding and all other miscellaneous operations in crossbred cattle it was observed to be 27.46MM (20.35%), 41.79MM (30.98%) and 65.66MM (48.67%) respectively. Among the buffaloes the respective contribution on these activities were 21.86MM (17.16%) 42.88MM (33.19%) and 63.24MM (49.65%). In case of local cattle the proportionate time was consumed in milking 16.30MM (16.12%), in feeding 33.73MM (33.26%) and all miscellaneous activities 51.08MM (50.52%)

Bhinda Rashmi et.al (2021) The findings showed that labour employed 14.05MM for milking operation 9.85MM for cleaning operation 10.06MM for feeding and 0.97MM for miscellaneous activities.

Methodology Primary data were collected from 240 milk producing entrepreneurs from different villages of Moradabad district of western U.P. Covering all the diverse tehsils and all the blocks. The data so called were bifurcated on the basis of P.CDF Cooperative and Non PCDF (Non Cooperative) Primarily and categories were assigned on the basis of holding size in both the sectors. For the analysis of seasonal impact the data were collected thrice i.e, in all the three seasons namely from March to June (summer season), July to October (rainy season) and November to February (winter season) we observed that bigger the holding size bigger was the herd as per the standard Adult Unit's (SAUs) for the animals as under.

Buffalo in milk = 1 unit

Buffalo dry = 0.4 unit

Local cow in milk = 0.7 unit

Local cow dry = 0.3 unit

Crossbred cow in milk = 1.4 unit

Crossbred Cow dry = 1.0 unit

Heifer = 0.5 unit

Young stock = 0.2 unit

(Male & Female)

Draught dairy animal = 0.5 Unit

The weight assigned for the conversion of female and child labour into uniform man-equivalent the following formula was applied.

2 Males = 3 Females

1 Male = 1.5 Females

1 Male = 2 Children

All the Man-minute were calculated after the balancing of man powers converted deployed on the above Yard stick.

Result and Discussion

Dairying as a whole comprises the activity of cattle grazing, bringing grass & fodder, Chaffing, feeding, Milking, watering & bathing, cleaning of Cattle shed and last but not least miscellaneous. This study was conducted to analysis or investigate the impact of cooperative sectors over non cooperative sector just to reach the differential and relative yield i.e, the final goal of all the activities combined. Activity wise as well as category wise and season wise analysis revealed the following results.

Cattle grazing In PCDF sector this activity was found to be performed by landless labourer category only, the time Consumed for the same came out to be 8.26MM, 12.17 MM and 9.72 MM per milch animal per day for summer, rainy, and winter season respectively. The overall for the category was calculated as 10.65MM and the relative percentage were 7.44, 7.12 and 6.01 for all the three seasons and 6.80% for all the three seasons collectively. The data reflected that more time for this activity is required during rainy season as there is abundance of green grass etc during this season.

Under non PCDF sector this activity is seen in respect of the first to categories only. Basically landless labourers resort to cattle grazing and average time per milch stock per day was computed as 8.90MM. It was also observed that the categories of marginal former as shown in the table is also in the practice of cattle grazing during rainy season only and man-minute required for this activity came out to be 4.04 per milch animal per day in respect of this category. Overall average for the pool thus comes to 2.05 M.M only with equivalent relative percentage of 2.62 only.

If we go per the impact it was observed that time consumed in this activity is far higher in case of PCDF sector in comparison to non PCDF sector. Though all the five categories do not dependent on grazing yet we can infer that PCDF sector promote grazing for better yield as and when possible.

Bringing grass and fodder- Under PCDF sector the relative share of this activity was 21.43% for the sector as a whole and drastic variation was observed in the season wise figures the figures being 15.98%, during the summer season 21.04% during rainy season and 24.79% during the winter season. This signified that maximum time Consumed for this activity was during the winter season followed by the rainy season while the least in summer season, Categories wise relative percentage were observed that 25.83% 23.49%, 19.02% 17.32% and 14.77% for all the five categories respectively. The implication was that as the category size advances relative proportional of cost deteriorate marginally. It is all because of the maxim of collective higher utility.

Under non PCDF sector this activity was observed to consume 19.88% for the pool while relative percentages for all the five categories were 23.66%, 21.16%, 18.48%, 16.29% and 13.60% for all the five categories. It we compare on the basis of absolute Man-minute the table reflects that this activity is also requires more time in PCDF sector in comparison to non PCDF sector in respect of all the categories.

Chaffing - Under PCDF sector chaffing was observed to require 7.31MM, 19.93MM and 20.00MM for summer, rainy and winter season respectively. This drastic difference was observed for time Consumed in this activity during different seasons. This activity consumed 16 percent total time as a whole but the relative percentages for all the three seasons were 12.46%, 15.14% and 18.17%, for summer, rainy and winter seasons respectively, Categories figures as depicted in the table confirm the same trend that this activity takes the least time during the summer season as green grass and fodder are scares during the season. category wise figures were 18.22/12.32%, 20.37/16.61%, 15.92/16.81%, 12.24/17.92% and 11.98/20.41%, for all the five categories for all the three seasons combined.